

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from the Bremen Ship, Germany.

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Introduction

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from the Bremen Ship was carried out in the 1960s, at a time when dendrochronology as a discipline in Northern Europe was just beginning. Extensive tree-ring datasets for oaks had not yet been built, but nevertheless tree-ring curves from three timbers from the ship were successfully dated (Liese & Bauch 1965; Bauch 1969). A re-assessment of the curves in Bauch (1969), to examine the provenance for these timbers, found that Bauch's conclusion, that the timber had come from some distance up the Weser River, could be confirmed (Daly 2007, 115-116 and diagrams 113).

However, in order to examine the history of the procurement of timber for the Bremen Ship in sufficient detail, a more extensive analysis was proposed in 2015, and this project was made possible by a generous grant from the Förderverein Deutsches Schiffahrtsmuseum. The results of this analysis are described in this report.

Reassessment of the previous study

As mentioned above, a re-assessment of the previous analysis reaches the same conclusion as Bauch. The dating of the two timbers is confirmed (fig. 1) and comparing the two trees with an extensive dataset for oaks in Northern Europe (figs. 2 & 3) it can be seen that the highest correlations are with Upper Weser chronologies.

Fig. 1. Bremen Ship, previous analysis. Dendrochronological dating of timbers from the Bremen Ship (after Bauch 1969)

Fig. 2. Bremen Ship. Provenance of Bauch's timber 1, reassessed. The yellow square marks the find location of the ship. The sizes of the blue and green dots indicate the correlation (t -value) between the tree-ring curve from timber 1 and each site or master chronology. The bigger the dot, the higher the correlation. The highest t -values are also printed in text form.

Fig. 3. Bremen Ship. Provenance of Bauch's timber 2, reassessed. The yellow square marks the find location of the ship. The sizes of the blue and green dots indicate the correlation (t -value) between the tree-ring curve from timber 2 and each site or master chronology. The bigger the dot, the higher the correlation. The highest t -values are also printed in text form.

The measurements from the earlier dendrochronological study were also derived from the diagrams in this publication (Liese & Bauch 1965). The curve from the timber is 99 years in length but it has not been possible to confirm the dated position for this timber, nor to identify any other dating position for it. For the purposes of this new research, this timber is now considered undated.

New analysis

The strategy for a new analysis of the Bremen Ship was to sample as much as possible a wide variety of the ship's constructional components. Sampling was carried out by coring, using a specially designed borer that bores a hole in the timber 16mm in diameter, and to a maximum depth of 30 cm. the core extracted is 6mm wide. The position of the coring is aimed at maximizing the number of rings retained in the core, from outermost towards the original centre of the tree. The timbers are assembled in the reconstructed ship, so sampling took place, during 19-22 April 2016, on in situ timbers chiefly inboard in the hull, but a few were also taken of hull planks from outboard. Care was taken to spread the sampling around the hull, so that a representative sample of timbers was achieved. Some timbers were sampled twice, to ensure a reliable tree-ring series. A list of all analysed samples is found in the catalogue, at the end of this report.

Dating

Of 78 analysed timbers 55 have been successfully dated (including the three from Bauch's analysis). (A small number of cores were not analysed, as they contained too few tree-rings, or were too fragmentary.) The chronological position of the tree-ring curves for each of the dated timbers is shown in fig. 4. In most timbers, only heartwood is observed, and the dating for the felling of each tree that these timbers come from is indicated in the illustration with an arrow, indicating a felling date after a certain year. The specific estimated felling dates for each timber are given in the catalogue at the end of this report, but this detail is not included in the illustration to keep the diagram clean and to the point. Bauch's estimated building date for the Bremen Ship, at around AD 1380, is marked with a vertical red line. All the new analyses are in full agreement with Bauch's conclusion. In other words, no evidence of later additions to the ship has emerged in this analysis. This underlines the interpretation that this ship was not an old ship when it sank. Of all the dated samples, just three have sapwood preserved. One of the timbers sampled by Bauch had complete sapwood to bark edge, but this was not the case for any timbers examined in this analysis.

Groups

Using the correlation between every dated tree-ring curve with every other, shown in table 1, the material can be divided into a small number of groups. The groups are shown with different colours, and averages for each group have been calculated. The colours for each group are also repeated in the chronological diagram (fig. 4). The groups are a mixture of different components from the ship. No apparent differentiation can be made between the planks and the bulk timbers.

Fig. 4. Bremen Ship. Diagram showing the chronological position of the dated timbers. The vertical red line indicates the overall dating interpretation. The colours of the bars correspond to the groups defined in the analysis (see table 1).

Provenance

Group 1 (green) is the largest group and it is made from the tree-ring curves from 34 timbers. It is 243 years in full length but a version is made where the average is a minimum of five trees in depth, and this is 164 years in length, and covers the period AD 1186 to 1349. The correlation between the average for this group and a wide range of site and master chronologies is mapped in fig. 5 (and also shown in table 2). The group is achieving highest correlation with datasets around the Bremen hinterland. This seems to indicate that the bulk of timber for the building of the ship was harvested local to the ship-building site.

Fig. 5. Bremen Ship. Provenance of group 1. The yellow square marks the find location of the ship. The sizes of the blue and green dots indicate the correlation (*t*-value) between the average curve for group 1 (Z0072M05) and each site or master chronology. The bigger the dot, the higher the correlation. The highest *t*-values are also printed in text form.

Group 2 (blue) is made from just ten trees. Most are bulk timber, but a pair of ceiling planks are also assigned to this group. The full length of the average for group 2 (Z0072M06) is 262 years, but again a reduced version, only including the period where at least 5 trees are represented, is made and this is 156 years long, covering the period AD 1163 to 1318. As the correlation between this group and site and master chronologies indicates (mapped in fig. 6 and also shown in table 2) again a source area around the Bremen hinterland is likely.

Fig. 6. Bremen Ship. Provenance of group 2. The yellow square marks the find location of the ship. The sizes of the blue and green dots indicate the correlation (t -value) between the average curve for group 2 (Z0072M06) and each site or master chronology. The bigger the dot, the higher the correlation. The highest t -values are also printed in text form.

The two large groups also match each other, producing a t -value of 7.25.

The third average (Z0272M07) consists of just two timbers – the keel plank and one ceiling. As shown in table 2, the highest correlation between this average and Northern European chronologies is with the Doel 1, found in Belgium but made from timber from the Weser region (Haneca & Daly 2014).

The remaining timbers that have not been assigned to a group are all dating also with chronologies for Lower Saxony.

The provenance analysis of the Bremen Ship presents no evidence of long distance transport of timber for her construction, apart from the two earlier analysed timbers by Bauch.

To estimate the felling date of the oak a sapwood statistic for Northern Germany has been used. Oaks here have, on average, 20 (-5 +10) sapwood years (Hollstein 1980)). For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t -value (" t -test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed.

Filenames	-	-	Group 1 Z0072M05 5deep	Group 2 Z0072M06 5deep	Z0072M07	
-	start	dates	AD 1186	AD 1163	AD 1153	
-	dates	end	AD 1349	AD 1318	AD 1280	
German chronologies						
DM200006	AD 914	AD 1873	9.71	10.21	4.41	Lüneburger Heide (Göttingen Uni)
DM200005	AD 915	AD 1873	9.92	10.13	4.63	Niedersachsen Nord (Göttingen Uni)
DM200004	30 BC	AD 1960	8.42	8.84	3.13	G Weser (Göttingen Uni)
G350PZ01	AD 967	AD 1381	10.23	8.61	3.84	Truheng 46 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DM200001	AD 1082	AD 1972	9.67	5.19	4.41	Nieders. Kuestenraum (Göttingen Uni)
DM100008	AD 457	AD 1723	5.91	8.16	3.14	Lübeck (Hamburg Uni)
G3513Z01	AD 1042	AD 1328	7.07	7.67	-	Medingen 6 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DM100003	AD 436	AD 1968	4.70	7.20	3.02	Schleswig-Holstein (Hamburg Uni)
G5701Z01	AD 1138	AD 1330	6.92	6.81	-	Warburg 2 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G351WZ01	AD 1084	AD 1354	4.80	6.80	-	Suderburg 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
G3175Z01	AD 1135	AD 1264	-	6.22	-	Einbeck 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
DM200003	AD 1004	AD 1970	6.90	6.08	-	Weserbergland (Göttingen Uni)
G3711Z01	AD 1251	AD 1333	7.09	5.90	-	Ostbense 4 timbers (Göttingen Uni revised Daly 2007)
Low Countries chronologies						
nlmidden	AD 1023	AD 1666	6.92	8.37	4.00	Mid Netherlands (Jansma pers comm)
FLmedraw	AD 808	AD 1530	6.49	5.67	-	Flanders medieval raw (Haneca pers comm)
Polish chronologies						
P671001M	AD 980	AD 1347	4.75	7.70	4.45	PL Elblag (Wazny pers comm)
PP122M01	AD 1006	AD 1359	3.72	6.81	3.53	PL Elblag 114 timbers (Wazny pers comm revised Daly 2007)
P676001M	AD 1067	AD 1393	4.26	6.39	-	PL Kolobrzeg (Wazny pers comm)
Danish chronologies						
4M000001	AD 1058	AD 1350	5.49	7.47	4.64	Danmark Svendborg (Nationalmuseet)
PM670108	AD 725	AD 1985	4.25	7.26	4.47	PL Gdansk (Wazny pers comm)
ZEALAND0	AD 452	AD 1770	7.57	7.24	-	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
JUTLAND6	AD 846	AD 1793	7.74	7.23	4.29	Jutland 452 timbers (Daly unpubl)
8127M001	AD 846	AD 1771	6.38	6.49	4.31	Ålborg Østerå + Boulevarden 67 timbers (Daly 2000 2001a)
9M456781	109 BC	AD 1986	6.57	5.61	3.64	Jylland/Fyn (Nationalmuseet)
2121M002	AD 1052	AD 1596	7.63	5.29	-	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001c)
D010M001	AD 1100	AD 1282	7.13	5.28	-	Odense Adelige Jomfrukloster brønd 2 timbers (Daly 2011a)
70314M01	AD 1168	AD 1355	6.40	4.67	3.19	Skjern Bro 20 timbers (Daly 2001b 2006)
Ship chronologies						
doel1_all_m2	AD 1150	AD 1305	10.00	10.06	6.64	Ship timbers DOEL 1 (Haneca & Daly 2014)
02071M01	AD 1126	AD 1414	3.81	6.68	-	Dokøen Vrag 2 (Eriksen 2001)
Z076m003 all	AD 1097	AD 1393	4.35	6.42	3.09	Skjernøysund 3 all 19 timbers (Daly 2011b)
CLS2000	AD 1110	AD 1393	3.83	6.02	-	Hull Chapel Lane Yorkshire 11 boat planks (Tyers pers comm)
Chronologies of IMPORTS						
HMC_T165	AD 1078	AD 1369	5.19	7.10	3.08	Hull boards from 37 coffins Yorkshire (Tyers pers comm)
H118HM02	AD 1073	AD 1300	4.78	6.48	-	Kiel. Alte Feuerwac 5 timbers (Hamburg Uni revised Daly 2007)
60132M01	AD 1110	AD 1368	5.37	6.38	-	Boringholm barrels 6 timbers (Daly 2005)

Table 2. Bremen Ship. Table of correlation (t -values) between the three average curves for the ship and a range of master and site chronologies for oak for Northern Europe.

Discussion

The material used to build the Bremen Ship does not display strong homogeneity, but this phenomenon might not necessarily be because the material used for the ship comes from a wide geographical area. The trees could equally be from a quite open landscape, where trees have less competition and thus their growth is less subject to limiting factors, thus reducing somewhat the common regional climate signal. A similar level of

low internal agreement is seen in the material used to build the Doel 1 Ship, which is from AD 1325/26, which is in fact built of oaks from a similar region to the Bremen Ship timbers (Haneca & Daly 2014).

The planking timbers used to build the ship have extensive knots and distortion and it is clear from the material that cracks already appeared in these planks, during the manufacture of the ship. Cracks show clear remains of caulking and sintels. Planks on the more extensively preserved and examined starboard side are often 7 to 9 metres long, but half way along their length the knots are very sizeable. It is surmised that these planks were made from trees whose main trunk was not long enough for making high quality planking – from trees in a less closed landscape. Trees that are not competing for light tend to grow shorter than trees in a dense forest. The dendrochronological evidence, showing that the trees for bulk timber components and planking came from the same region, coupled with the observations of knots and repairs to the hull in antiquity, suggests that the landscape around Bremen already in the 1370s was perhaps suffering from a shortage of timber suitable for making quality planks.

Planks for the Doel 1 Ship, built some 50 years earlier, do not have the same amount of knots. In the region around Bremen, trees that could be made into quality planking, suitable for bending to form a hull, were still available to shipbuilders. Perhaps the Bremen Ship never sailed because she was built of unsuitable planking material that very quickly cracked and distorted when bent. In spite of attempts to repair the cracks that started to appear, the damage was too extensive and the ship must have been abandoned.

Literature

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave. ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
<i>Samples, oak</i>											
Z007001a	Bremen Ship Stamm II	128	AD 1251	AD 1378	?	20	Y	?	N	1,21	AD 1378
Z007002a	Bremen Ship Stamm III	62	AD 1240	AD 1301	?	0	N	?	N	2,13	after AD 1316
Z007003a	Bremen Ship (Liese Bauch 1965)	99			G	0	N	?	N	1,00	undated
Z007101a	D01 Bremen Ship deck crossbeam 3	166	AD 1182	AD 1347	G	0	N	?	H8	1,32	after AD 1370
Z007102a	D02 Bremen Ship cross beam 4	48			G	0	N	S	H1	3,08	undated
Z007103a	D03 Bremen Ship frame 41.1	21			V	0	N	?	H1	5,13	undated
Z007104a	D04 Bremen Ship cross beam 5	110	AD 1251	AD 1360	G	0	N	?	N	1,74	after AD 1375
Z007105a	D05 Bremen Ship windlass support ST	81	AD 1177	AD 1257	G	0	N	?	H1	1,46	after AD 1273
Z007106a	D06 Bremen Ship stringer SB	133	AD 1125	AD 1257	G	0	N	?	H1	1,53	after AD 1273
Z007107a	D07 Bremen Ship ceiling above stringer aft SB	188	AD 1131	AD 1318	G	0	N	?	H1	0,59	after AD 1334
Z0071089	D08 Bremen Ship futtock frame 40	65			G	0	N	?	H1	0,94	undated
Z007109a	D09 Bremen Ship windlass	156	AD 1099	AD 1254	G	0	N	?	H1	0,98	after AD 1270
Z007110a	D10 Bremen Ship frame 43.1	82	AD 1253	AD 1334	F	0	N	?	H1	0,94	after AD 1350
Z007112a	D12 Bremen Ship deckbeam central castle	28			G	0	N	?	H1	3,72	undated
Z0071139	D13 Bremen Ship hull plank 11.3 SB 113&183 same plank	116	AD 1229	AD 1344	G	0	N	?	N	1,43	after AD 1360
Z007114a	D14 Bremen Ship plank 12.3	86	AD 1254	AD 1339	G	0	N	?	H1	1,44	after AD 1355
Z007116a	D16 Bremen Ship plank 8.3 PB	64	AD 1155	AD 1218	G	0	N	?	H1	1,93	after AD 1234
Z007117a	D17 Bremen Ship rudder cross beam	86	AD 1243	AD 1328	G	0	N	?	N	1,14	after AD 1343
Z007118a	D18 Bremen Ship futtock 38 PS	164	AD 1186	AD 1349	G	0	N	?	H1	0,54	after AD 1365
Z007119a	D19 Bremen Ship futtock frame 38 sb	103	AD 1240	AD 1342	G	0	N	?	H1	0,91	after AD 1358
Z007120a	D20 Bremen Ship ceiling plank 2.1 SB aft	104	AD 1209	AD 1312	F	0	N	?	H1	1,81	after AD 1328
Z007121a	D21 Bremen Ship ceiling 3.3 SB aft	90	AD 1261	AD 1350	G	0	N	?	H1	1,67	after AD 1366
Z007122a	D22 Bremen Ship ceiling 2.3 PS	83	AD 1253	AD 1335	G	0	N	?	H1	1,70	after AD 1366
Z007123a	D23 Bremen Ship frame 36 floor	49			G	0	N	?	N	2,04	undated
Z007124a	D24 Bremen Ship frame 42.1.2	29			G	0	N	O	H1	3,24	undated
Z0071269	D26 Bremen Ship frame 35	65			F	0	N	?	H1	0,84	undated
Z007127a	D27 Bremen Ship frame 35 futtock PB	107			G	0	N	?	H1	0,64	undated
Z0071289	D28 Bremen Ship strake 3.5 SB	84	AD 1213	AD 1296	G	0	N	?	H1	1,74	after AD 1312
Z007129a	D29 Bremen Ship strake 2.3	57	AD 1281	AD 1337	G	0	N	?	H1	2,09	after AD 1353
Z007131a & b	D31 Bremen Ship strake 1 SB	40 & 26			G	0	N	T	H1	2,2 & 1,3	undated
Z007132a	D32 Bremen Ship ceiling plank 3.2 SB aft	110	AD 1167	AD 1276	G	0	N	?	H1	1,42	after AD 1292
Z007133a	D33 Bremen Ship futtock PS 34	74	AD 1271	AD 1344	G	0	N	?	H1	1,22	after AD 1360
Z007134a	D34 Bremen Ship ceiling 4.2 PS	71	AD 1207	AD 1277	G	0	N	?	N	1,50	after AD 1292
Z007135a	D35 Bremen Ship hull plank 8.3 aft	101	AD 1209	AD 1309	G	0	N	?	H1	2,20	after AD 1325
Z007136a	D36 Bremen Ship futtock 32 PS	113	AD 1223	AD 1335	V	0	N	?	H1	0,92	after AD 1351
Z0071379	D37 Bremen Ship futtock PS33	83	AD 1261	AD 1343	F	0	N	O	H1	0,90	after AD 1359
Z007138a	D38 Bremen Ship frame 33 floor	69	AD 1282	AD 1350	G	0	N	?	H1	1,31	after AD 1366
Z0071392	D39 Bremen Ship Futtock Frame 33 SB D39	88			?	0	N	?	N	0,35	undated
Z007140a	D40 Bremen Ship ceiling plank 4.4 SB aft	38	AD 1285	AD 1322	G	0	N	?	N	2,53	after AD 1337
Z007141a	D41 Bremen Ship frame 31 futtock PS	51			G	0	N	?	H1	1,38	undated
Z0071429	D42 Bremen Ship frame 31 floor D42	99	AD 1222	AD 1320	G	0	N	?	N	1,26	after AD 1335
Z007143a	D43 Bremen Ship frame 31 futtock SB	118			G	0	N	?	N	0,72	undated
Z0071449	D44 Bremen Ship floor frame 30	110			V	0	N	?	H1	1,01	undated
Z007145a	D45 Bremen Ship futtock frame 30 sb	121	AD 1214	AD 1334	G	0	N	?	H1	0,87	after AD 1350
Z007146a	D46 Bremen Ship ceiling 6.3 SB	84	AD 1147	AD 1230	G	0	N	?	H1	1,63	after AD 1246

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Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave. ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Z007147a	D47 Bremen Ship 2nd futtock frame 30 sb	56	AD 1299	AD 1354	G	0	N	?	N	1,42	after AD 1369
Z0071489	D48 Bremen Ship keel plank 148b&149 same timber	128	AD 1153	AD 1280	G	0	N	?	H1	1,61	after AD 1296
Z007150a	D50 Bremen Ship frame 23 floor	24			G	0	N	?	H1	2,17	undated
Z007151a	D51 Bremen Ship bow knee	104	AD 1251	AD 1354	G	0	N	?	H1	1,91	after AD 1370
Z007152a	D52 Bremen Ship floor frame 0	25			G	0	N	?	H1	1,83	undated
Z007153a	D53 Bremen Ship floor frame 0	31			G	0	N	?	N	1,76	undated
Z007154a	D54 Bremen Ship inner stempost SB frem	75	AD 1263	AD 1337	G	0	N	?	H1	0,99	after AD 1353
Z0071559	D55 Bremen Ship PS inner stem post	140	AD 1163	AD 1302	G	0	N	?	H1	1,03	after AD 1318
Z007156c	D56 Bremen Ship inner stempost SB	159	AD 1180	AD 1338	G	0	N	?	H1	0,84	after AD 1354
Z007157a	D57 Bremen Ship floor frame 2	135	AD 1216	AD 1350	G	0	N	?	N	0,90	after AD 1365
Z007158a	D58 Bremen Ship hullplank 9.1 PS	112	AD 1232	AD 1343	G	0	N	?	H1	1,46	after AD 1359
Z007159a	D59 Bremen Ship floor frame 3	129	AD 1219	AD 1347	G	0	N	?	H1	1,02	after AD 1363
Z007160a	D60 Bremen Ship frame 1 floor	121	AD 1193	AD 1313	G	0	N	?	H1	1,03	after AD 1329
Z007161a	D61 Bremen Ship futtock frame 1 SB	96	AD 1246	AD 1341	G	0	N	?	H1	0,54	after AD 1357
Z007162a	D62 Bremen Ship futtock frame 2 SB	91			F	0	N	?	H1	1,54	undated
Z0071639	D63 Bremen Ship toptimber on deckbeam 1 SB	153	AD 1163	AD 1315	F	0	N	?	H1	0,69	after AD 1331
Z0071649	D64 Bremen Ship bollard at crossbeam 1 SB	103	AD 1190	AD 1292	G	0	N	?	H1	1,13	after AD 1308
Z007165a	D65 Bremen Ship deckbeam 1	74	AD 1294	AD 1367	G	15	N	?	S1	1,33	AD 1368-82
Z007166a	D66 Bremen Ship stringer SB bow top	47			G	0	N	?	H1	2,82	undated
Z007167a&b	D67 Bremen Ship frame 6 2nd futtock SB	49 & 48			G	0	N	?	N	0,92	undated
Z007168a	D68 Bremen Ship floor frame 7	115	AD 1232	AD 1346	G	5	N	?	N	0,72	AD 1356-71
Z007169a	D69 Bremen Ship floor frame 8	64	AD 1278	AD 1341	G	0	N	?	H1	1,43	after AD 1357
Z007170a	D70 Bremen Ship strake 4.1 PS	81	AD 1216	AD 1296	G	0	N	?	H1	1,47	after AD 1312
Z007171a	D71 Bremen Ship strake 5.1 PS	35			G	0	N	?	H1	2,57	undated
Z007172a	D72 Bremen Ship hull plank 3.1 PS	70	AD 1246	AD 1315	G	0	N	?	H1	2,63	after AD 1331
Z007173a	D73 Bremen Ship 1st futtock frame 9 ps	67			G	0	N	?	H1	1,75	undated
Z007174a	D74 Bremen Ship frame 9 1st futtock SB	91	AD 1242	AD 1332	G	0	N	?	H1	1,13	after AD 1348
Z007175a	D75 Bremen Ship frame 9 2nd.futtock	40			F	0	N	?	H1	2,40	undated
Z007176a	D76 Bremen Ship hull plank 8.2 SB	146	AD 1202	AD 1347	G	0	N	?	H1	2,08	after AD 1363
Z007179b	D79 Bremen Ship hull plank 9.3 SB	60	AD 1273	AD 1332	G	0	N	?	N	1,11	after AD 1347
Z007182a	D82 Bremen Ship hull plank 11.2 SB	102	AD 1248	AD 1349	G	0	N	?	H1	1,05	after AD 1365
Z007184a	D84 Bremen Ship hull plank 12.2 SB	36	AD 1252	AD 1287	G	0	N	?	N	1,69	after AD 1356
Z007184b	D84 Bremen Ship hull plank 12.2 SB	46	AD 1296	AD 1341	G	0	N	?	N	1,00	after AD 1356
Z0071869	D86 Bremen Ship hull plank 7.1 SB	101	AD 1147	AD 1247	G	0	N	?	H1	1,91	after AD 1263
Same tree											
Z007121&22 same tree	Bremen Ship ceilings 3.3sb & 2.3ps	98	AD 1253	AD 1350	G	0	N	?	N	1,68	after AD 1366
Averages											
Z0072M05 5deep	Bremen Ship group 1 34 timbers 5 tree depth (Daly 2017)	164	AD 1186	AD 1349						1,35	
Z0072M06 5deep	Bremen Ship group 2 10 timbers 5 tree depth (Daly 2017)	156	AD 1163	AD 1318						0,95	
Z0072M07	Bremen Ship group 3 2 timbers (Daly 2017)	128	AD 1153	AD 1280						1,58	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			23rd September 2017								

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